

Perspectives On Green Accounting And Its Relationship With Sustainable Development In The Business

Nguyen Phu Giang, Tran Nguyen Bich Hien, Vu Thi Thu Huyen, Luong Thi Hong Ngan, Dao Ngoc Ha

Article Info

Article History

Received:
May , 2021

Accepted:
December , 2021

Keywords :

Environmental Accounting (EA), Environmental management accounting (EMA), Green Design, Green Accounting (GA)

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5810650

Abstract

Purpose – This study synthesizes macro and micro perspectives on green accounting, some measurement methods used in green accounting such as environmental cost measurement, product life cycle cost measurement, Activity Based Costing method (ABC). The article also analyzed that the application of green accounting can lead to implementing a "green" design for the production process. The research also shows that applying for green accounting benefits the sustainable development of both businesses and society, thereby promoting businesses to voluntarily apply green accounting. The article also identified and measured the factors affecting the application of green accounting in enterprises, proved that the application of green accounting affects sustainable development in enterprises.

Methodology – We collected data on 195 manufacturing enterprises, in 6 sectors. The main data analysis method used for this study is the SEM structural equation modeling method. The article used AMOS software to evaluate and measure the influence of each factor on the application of green accounting in enterprises. By dividing the group of businesses that have applied GA and have not applied GA, we have used the Independent-Samples T-Test method and successfully demonstrated that the application of GA has an impact on the sustainability of the business.

Findings – We have discovered that to apply green accounting in businesses, it is necessary to have a "green" design for the product. This will help businesses implement green accounting to avoid environmental impact but still ensure economic goals. We have also successfully demonstrated that green accounting if implemented, will bring benefits to both businesses and society

Practical implications – Green accounting has shown that the rational use of resources is essential. The measurement and record of green accounting have also shown that we are disrupting the ecological environment without recreating the environment.

Social implications: Research has shown that if we don't protect the ecological environment, we live by capital, not by added value.

Originality/value - Outlining the logic of green accounting, it is necessary to have a "green" design for the product to apply green accounting, and to increase the sustainability of the business

Introduction

Many environmental costs can be significantly reduced or eliminated through business decisions, from adopting clean manufacturing to investing in processes or products with green technology. The green industry is the key issue of sustainable development (Cucchiella, F., D'Adamo, I., Gastaldi, M., Lenny, K.S. and Rosa, P., 2017). Environmental change is always a global problem and requires global solutions. Green accounting is considered an important management system that helps to activate and improve the economic and environmental performance of enterprises.

Green accounting is a type of accounting that incorporates environmental factors into the financial results of an enterprise (De Beer, P. and Friend, F., 2006). Green accounting requires a multidisciplinary knowledge of behavior, engineering, sociology, and even biology. The basic premise of green accounting is environmental cost accounting. The objective of green accounting is to record and measure to reduce the negative impacts of activities and systems on the environment. The most important role of green accounting is to address social and environmental issues that can have an impact on achieving sustainable development (Chen, B., Dai, J. and Sciubba, E., 2014)

The article proved macro and micro perspectives on green accounting, an issue related to environmental and ecological science, and sustainable management of natural ecosystems. Green accounting is also a new idea and

concept in the fields of environmental accounting related to people, environmental management, and environmental policymaking. The article also aims to solve the problem of rational use of resources, stating the measurement and approach of green accounting such as measuring environmental costs, measuring costs by product life cycle, measuring costs by ABC method. The article also identified and measured the factors affecting the application of green accounting in enterprises, proved that the application of green accounting affects sustainable development in enterprises.

Green accounting and its impact on cost reduction as a tool to improve the internal view of any economic entity. It is also a tool for providing information critical to decision making, leading to optimal exploitation of resources, and protecting and preventing threats from the environment. The content of the article includes:

Perspectives on green accounting: a macro and micro perspective

The development of green accounting

Some views on measurement of green accounting: Measuring environmental costs, measuring costs by product life cycle, measuring by ABC method

Identify and measure the influence of factors on the application of green accounting in manufacturing enterprises in Vietnam and prove that the application of GA has an impact on sustainability in enterprises

2. Literature reviews

The term "green accounting" was first used by an economist, Professor Peter Wood, in 1980. Mr. Peter Wood has for the first time emphasized the necessity and importance of introducing green accounting in India. De Beer, P. and Friend, F., 2006, stated that: additional financial information should present the nature of the activities carried out under environmental projects at the end of the period in a certain period time. The research has shown the recommendations related to the most important issue of developing the financial accounting system of enterprises to be able to prepare environmental accounting reports and present quantitative and qualitative information and environmental costs. Although green accounting has become a worldwide norm, it is still in the testing phase in many countries. Along with sustainable development, green accounting needs to be mandatory in the future, which will affect the production of the product and increase operating costs, force businesses to redesign their products. This is studied by Kawakita Jiro, 1995 announced by the U.S.

Green accounting is a division of environmental management accounting. Green accounting promotes a sustainable future for businesses, passes the environmental costs into business financial results. Green accounting uses the Environmental-Economic Accounting System (SEEA), which focuses on depleting scarce natural resources and measures the costs of environmental degradation along with preventing it. The main purpose of green accounting is to help businesses understand and manage the potential relationship between traditional economic goals and environmental goals. It uses important information available to analyze policy issues related to the environment and sustainable development, especially policies on the use of natural resources.

The Japanese Ministry of Environment defines green accounting as "quantitative assessment of expenditures and benefits in environmental protection activities" and "systematically establishing records and reports, maintaining a positive relationship between businesses and natural ecosystems, promoting effective environmental practices to achieve sustainable development". Green accounting systems in EU countries, such as Denmark and the Netherlands, are required by law to disclose environmental information to the government. The countries that have not yet developed relevant laws, such as the United States and Japan, have required some businesses to disclose environmental information. In Taiwan, the government has released guidelines to promote a green accounting system. In Vietnam, the government enacted the Environmental Tax Act in 2010. Multinational corporations are increasingly concerned about whether their suppliers disclose green accounting information before proceeding with the transactions. According to Paul P. Craig, Harold Glasser, 1994, the explanation for green accounting can be explained by natural phenomena. Every living thing and animal needs habitat, healthy food, clean water, proper range, minimal survival population, etc. If these and other basic conditions cannot be provided, the species is likely to become extinct. These issues help us discover the prerequisites for sustainability. The natural capital needs to be improved, which is a problem drawn from sustainability and is the research goal of green accounting. Two clear principles of sustainable development: Firstly, the harvest rate should be equal to (or less than) the regeneration rate (sustainable yield). Secondly, the rate of waste emissions must be equal to (or less than) the natural assimilation capacity of the ecosystems to which they have been released. The regeneration and assimilation capacities must be considered as natural capital, and failure to maintain these capacities must be considered a capital expenditure, and therefore unsustainable. According to Turner, P., and Tschirhart, J. (2017), these two "common sense" principles for the establishment of sustainable policies differ from traditional economic indicators in that they are biogeophysical based. To make these principles operationally useful, a business must have actual inventory and flow data. They suggested that when the issue at hand is sustainability, economic valuation techniques are often too decoupled from the biogeophysical issues to provide us with the necessary insights. Green accounting cannot focus on renewable resources alone. Complex trade-offs and substitutions may be consistent with sustainability. It is important to recognize that Daly's guidelines are preliminary and not absolute. They are used to illustrate the

efficacy of considering a biogeophysical-based approach to natural capital accounting. This may be desirable from a development perspective. Harvesting of nonrenewables may, in certain instances, prove to be more "sustainable" than harvesting some resource sustainably.

Country and name	Regulations or definitions
Denmark, 1995 Green Accounts Act	About 1200 enterprises with high pollution must publish green accounting reports, 200 enterprises voluntarily provide green accounting reports
Netherlands, 1999 Environmental Management Act	About 260 enterprises are required to publish environmental reports, 40 voluntarily provide environmental accounting reports.
U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 1995 An Introduction to GA As A Business Management Tool	Environmental cost accounting means additional environmental information into the current cost accounting system and allocated environmental costs for products
UN Division for Sustainable Development 2001 Environmental Management Accounting (EMA)	EMA can provide information on production costs, product design, and investment for decision-making. An accounting information system that allows companies to manage environmental costs in the product lifecycle to have a strategy to protect the environment
International Federation of Accountants, 2005 Environmental Management Accounting Guidelines	Environmental management accounting (EMA) manages environmental management and economic performance by developing and implementing an appropriate GA system, including reports and financial statement audits and environmental audits. Green accounting includes life cycle accounting, total cost accounting, effective environmental management planning.
Ministry of the Environment, Japan, 2005 Environmental Accounting Guidelines	Green accounting is a quantitative assessment of the costs and efficiency of enterprises in environmental protection activities. Enterprises are required to have systematic records and reports and be guided to maintain a positive relationship with the ecological environment to perform effective activities. The ultimate goal is to realize sustainable development.
Environmental Protection Administration, Taiwan, 2008 Industrial Environmental Accounting Guidelines	By measuring, recording, analyzing, and interpreting, the company's resources are used to improve and protect the environment. The operating process is completely reorganized and consistent, the results are delivered to the stakeholders of the business

Table 1 - The development of green accounting (Farouk, S., Cherian, J. and Jacob, J., 2012)

3. Theoretical framework of research

3.1. Perspectives on green accounting

Green accounting on a macro perspective

The core idea underpinning Pearce and Turner's "sustainability principle" is the hypothesis of a scalar quantity "the amount of natural capital". However, according to them, the concept of natural capital in green accounting needs to be reconsidered. Why should the concept of natural capital exist? If it does exist, in what fields should it be determined, and for what period? How to fully reflect the functional integrity of ecosystems, species diversity, ecosystem health, the economic value of natural resources, and the quality of human life in one optimal equation?

Paul P. Craig, Harold Glasser studied green accounting starting with national income accounts, then they considered several econometric approaches designed to internalize environmental externalities. In the study of intergenerational sustainability, almost all economic analysis uses the concept of the time value of money, i.e. the use of a discount rate to convert the time value of money. However, according to them, the use of discount rates for green accounting is very vague. According to Mishan (1975) cited by Cline (1992), when there is a comparison between generations, the determination of social values at different times is not satisfactory. In other words, the rate of interest charged in the market is only for consumer loans.

Green accounting studies national income accounts. Most current national income accounts are based on the significant factors that can be expressed by a single number, usually currency. It is assumed that all physical and labor indicators are referred to as monetary indicators. This total, including "use value", "option value" and "survival value", is called the total economic value (TEV). The "use value" can be direct when goods and services are exchanged on the market that reveals their value. The use-value is indirect refers to the life support services role of the natural environment, which are 'indirectly used'. The option values reflect the value people place on a future ability to use the environment and thus the potential future benefits of goods and services. Quasi-option value reflects the willingness to avoid irreversible commitment to development now, given the expectation of future growth in knowledge relevant to the implications of development. There is no full agreement about considering option and quasi-option values among use or non-use values.

Non-use values include existence values, where the benefit results from the knowledge that goods and services exist and will continue to exist, independently of any actual or prospective use by the individual; and bequest value, where the benefit is in ensuring that future generations will be able to inherit the same goods and services of the present generation.

We have seen that passing on an "intact" resource, i.e. natural capital that remains unchanged over the next few generations, is central to the concept of sustainable economic development. A growth policy is primarily directed at satisfying human needs, as well as ensuring the survival of much of the surrounding nature. Therefore, it is only necessary to have adequate environmental protection measures in place without applying any radical arguments and ethics of 'deep ecology'. In particular, it is not necessary to accept notions of intrinsic value, but more concerned about environmental ethics, as well as meeting the goal of intergenerational equity (Pearce and Turner, 1990).

Green accounting on the perspective of business

The above are the views on green accounting from the macro perspective of the economy. However, to get macro indicators such as national income, gross domestic product..., businesses need to implement green accounting to provide indicators to aggregate into macro indicators. To be widely accepted, an improved accounting system must be able to cope with the enormous diversity of humanity and the global ecosystem. The reason for resource depletion is that raw materials are still produced, but natural resource extraction is still cheaper, so businesses tend to take advantage of this opportunity. From a sustainability view, businesses manage detailed physical accounts to ensure that they can meet our present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

To apply green accounting, it is necessary to restructure and innovate the accounting system of the enterprise, arrange and design the measuring components, record the material flows and loss of natural resources, measure costs, environmental income, the impact of business activities on the natural environment.

In the spirit of Ann Harrison's final recommendation presented at the Society UNEP-World Bank symposium (Harrison, 1989):

The accounting systems should be structured so that they "show for all capital—man-made, natural and human—the ratio of stock at the end of the period to that at the beginning." We made some observations at some survey enterprises to facilitate the implementation of green accounting and found that: Many types of measurement should be included in the green accounting system because it is necessary to measure and record diverse issues with a wide range and multi-criteria. In addition, a system of comprehensive and diverse performance evaluation criteria should also be built along with the system of green accounting accounts. Green accounting should be used in conjunction with econometric techniques to set goals and make short-term policy decisions. The setting up a green accounting model should focus on developing a range of indicators (Bernard, 1990; House, 1990; Huffman, 1990; Kuik, 1991). Many indicators of environmental quality were proposed in the 1970s by the Council on Environmental Quality (1981), and more recently by the World Resources Institute (1992) (OECD, 1991; Brown et al., 1993). The long-term indicators will be mainly biogeographic. The shorter-term indicators may have more weight on economics.

Green accountants also need to use the product life cycle assessment tool to measure the environmental impacts of business activities, promote clean production, through the assessment of total costs and combine the traditional accounting for corporate environmental financial disclosure. The green accounting system must be dynamic and flexible, structured so that the organization can update when there are new indicators and information from the environment and society. Green accounting systems must be linked to specific conceptual models of the interaction between the economy and the environment. The databases need to be built so that they are accessible to many types of delivery models, especially environmental models.

In addition, in the development of a green accounting system, it is necessary to focus on articulating and integrating conceptual frameworks in each of the areas that have many threats to sustainability such as agriculture, forestry, fisheries, climate, species diversity, air, water and soil quality, etc. Building a green accounting system in enterprises of this type requires the help of experts in each field. Experts can identify normative assumptions and key conceptual frameworks in their field. In the agricultural sector, for example, the involvement of household farmers, organic farmers (both large and small), business farmers, genetic engineers, and consumers, who have long experience in the field of sustainable agriculture is required. Each person may be asked to describe how they assess soil quality and soil degradation, considering short- and long-term threats to sustainability.

According to research by Stanojevic, M., Vranes (2010), the requirements of green accounting include expanding corporate social responsibility, production with the environmental protection, external production costs internalized, redesign to improve product manufacturing and packaging processes, reducing wasted resources, and implementing 3R policy (Reduce, Recycle, Reuse). All the contents of green accounting can only be solved with a green design. The green design is the reorganization of the product manufacturing process, product design to achieve environmental goals but still achieve profit goals.

3.2. Some theoretical issues about green accounting

Green accounting provides useful information for achieving cost reduction goals (especially environmental costs) and minimizing environmental impacts, presenting cost data needed to estimate financial impact. The measurement tools that can be applied in green accounting are:

- Measure and reflect environmental costs
- Measure and reflect life cycle costs in products
- Use the ABC method to reflect and measure environmental-related costs in each activity of the production process.

Measure and reflect environmental costs

Accountants determined the current state of the environment to measure the current environmental costs, measure the change in additional costs compared to the original status quo such as the cost of raw materials, direct labor, cost of use, etc. equipment, indirect costs related to the environment. The accounting measures costs to implement the provisions of the law and environmental commitments such as cleaning machines that emit harmful gases, damage to machinery, etc. In addition, environmental costs also have other indirect costs that accountants need to determine and measure such as compensation costs for parties, legal and judicial costs for individuals or property... The environmental costs are usually accounted for in two categories: capitalized costs to fixed assets and period costs.

Table 2 – Types of costs covered by green accounting

Description	Green Accounting Issues and Scope
Pollution Prevention Cost	Costs incurred to prevent air and water pollution along with water treatment facilities and other activities
Environmental Protection Costs	Costs of energy-saving measures as well as costs of global warming reduction measures
Costs of Resource Recycling	Costs incurred for waste reduction and disposal as well as for water conservation, rainwater usage, and other measures aimed at efficient resources usage
Environmental Restoration Costs	Cost of environmental restoration operations (eliminating soil and groundwater contamination, environmental compensation)
Management Costs	Management-related environmental protection costs including environmental promotion activities and costs associated with acquiring and maintaining ISO 14001 certification
Social Promotion Activities Costs	Environmental protection costs stemming from participation in social activities such as participation in organizations concerning environmental preservation etc
Research and Development Costs	Environmental protection costs for research and development activities and costs of environmental solutions business activities (Green product/environmental technology design and development costs, environmental solutions business costs, others)

Measure and reflect product lifecycle costs

Green accounting to reduce environmental costs, the first step is to measure environmental costs, the next step is to measure and reflect costs in the product life cycle.

Accountants need a product life cycle approach to define the scope of the product life cycle stages, especially environmental-related activities in the product life cycle. The product life cycle costing is the process of estimating and summarizing the costs incurred during the product life cycle. The product life cycle costs are usually the costs of treatment, waste disposal, environmental audits, etc. Determining product life cycle costs is very important, especially for industries with planned costs.

There are three benefits of lifecycle costing analysis: (1) Determining product lifecycle costs helps businesses understand whether profits are affected by costs in the development stage and exclusion of the product, (2) A product life cycle cost perspective can explain the environmental costs in the product and seek to reduce or limit the environmental costs, (3) Product life cycle costs specify costs in planning and exclusion in the 2 phases of design and production to control and manage costs in these stages.

The product lifecycle analysis helps to identify the causes of environmental pollution and how to prevent them throughout the product life cycle, specifically:

Product design phase: At this stage, enterprises need to pay attention to the alternatives that can be combined such as: Using recyclable materials, minimizing the use of toxic solvents or substituting other materials, reusing waste, using water-based materials instead of solvent materials, using a wide range of products and packaging requirements, producing a recyclable end product, etc. Hence, the major environmental costs in this phase can be costs of research and development activities necessary to meet the environmental requirements of the product, operational costs of product design or product manufacturing; cost of selecting or designing necessary components and materials for main components of products or services; cost analysis of risks related to the safety in the use of products, costs of analyzing product viability, reusability. Therefore, the biggest impact on environmental costs is incurred during the product design and development phase.

Raw material and energy purchasing stage

This period has a greater opportunity to reduce costs related to activities that have negative impacts on the environment such as reducing the cost of cleaning up the environment, the cost of treating environmental pollution... The environmental costs in this period include the cost of inspecting and surveying suppliers to consider and evaluate the ability to provide, as well as environmental requirements; costs for activities to ensure the implementation of technological processes suitable for the environment.

Production stage

The manufacturing process is a direct source of liquid, gaseous, and other wastes released into the environment. They can also arise due to the use of machines that pollute the environment

Packing stage

It can be seen that manufacturing is not the only source of environmental costs, but it also arises from the packaging phase. Therefore, it is important to focus on products for packaging, avoid products that are harmful to health, which can be reused.

Usage stage

The use of products with toxic emissions can cause water and soil pollution. This also stems from the materials used to make the product.

Product processing stage

After use, the product can be discarded, even though its components can be recycled or reused, it can still pollute the environment. Disposal costs and environmental impact will vary widely between product types. Therefore, we should take advantage of waste from the production process to reuse or recycle instead of disposing of it into the environment. This also reduces the overall cost of key products.

The study of environmental costs over the life of a product is the study of a type of preventive cost. There, these costs arise from activities performed at every stage of the product's life cycle to increase environmental performance and environmental pollution. The arising of these costs is to avoid the costs of dealing with environmental pollution or the costs of not complying with environmental requirements, compensation, and fines.

Use activity-based costing (ABC) to reflect and measure the cost

When applying green accounting, enterprises need to see the importance of the activity-based costing method to specifically allocate the environmental cost. The product lifecycle cost is the cost that is extremely important for industries where a lot of costs are incurred during the product development and exclusion stages.

The basic activity-based cost accounting system is a cost accounting system of resources consumed by activities. This is a more accurate method of cost measurement and is better than a traditional accounting system. ABC solves the problem of cost addition, by analyzing activity types, and then tracking costs for activities through cost allocation tools. The activities are classified into activities at the product level. Under the ABC method, a business can eliminate activities that do not create value for the intermediate product into products. Product activity is carried out to produce the product and attach importance to the benefit of this activity. Therefore, developing an activity-based costing system is usually based on the following assumptions:

- (1) Economic activities focus on resources and products;
- (2) The consumption of economic resources has many kernels;
- (3) Activity can be defined and measured;
- (4) There is uniformity among eligible expenses.

Based on this point, activity-based costing systems for products or services consume activities, activities consume resources. Then, the ABC method will help to achieve the three goals of cost accounting: clearly define cost quantity in detail, examine cost elements, provide information linkage for economic decision-making within the entity. The ABC method is suitable for products with many indirect costs in structural costing. The environmental costs are mostly indirect and applying the ABC method for environmental cost accounting is completely appropriate and achieves benefits such as: Calculating environmental costs for each product; eliminate or reduce operations for high-cost environments; reducing or eliminating products donated to the premium environment.

4. Research methods and results**4.1. Research sample**

We surveyed 195 enterprises via online questionnaires to identify and measure the factors affecting the application of GA in Vietnam by using AMOS data analysis software. The respondents to the survey are representatives of the board of directors in charge of finance and accounting. The period of survey and data collection was from September 2020 to April 2021. The main data analysis method used for this study was the structural equation modeling method (SEM) with AMOS - SPSS. To obtain a reliable estimate for this method, according to Tauchen (1986), the sample should usually be larger than 200 ($n > 200$). Based on the empirical rule of Hair et al. (2010), for one estimate variable, the minimum sample size needed for this study was $n > 8 \times$ number of variables = $8 \times 23 = 184$. Combining the above principles, the sample size, we choose with $n = 195$.

4.2. Identifying and measuring factors affecting the application of GA in enterprises

4.2.1. Research sample and variables: Statistics of the surveyed firms by industry sectors:

No.	Scope of activity	Number of firms	Proportion
1	Rubber processing	21	10.8%
2	Mineral	42	21.5%
3	Plastic packaging	32	16.4%
4	Fertilizer	19	9.7%
5	Steel manufacturing	26	13.3%
6	Food processing	55	26,7%
Total		195	100%

The research used variable of green accounting that measured by legal regulator system related to GA, characteristics of supply chain, strategy of business, enterprise accounting system (Turner, P. and Tschirhart, J. (2017), Leung Pah Hang, M.Y., Martinez-Hernandez, E., Leach, M. and Yang, A. (2016)). At the same time, the article also proved that the application of GA affected the sustainability of enterprises.

Table 3 – Variables affecting the application of GA and the level of sustainability of the business

	Legal regulatory system related to GA (DOCU)
1	Timeliness and suitability of the legal document system related to GA (DTIME)
2	Completeness of legal documents related to GA (DFULL)
3	The enforcement of the legal system of legal documents related to GA (DFORCE)
	Characteristics of the supply chain (CHAIN)
4	Pressure from supplier require businesses to apply GA (CHSUPP)
5	Pressure from customers require businesses to apply GA (CHCLIE)
6	Competitor pressure require businesses to apply GA (CHCOMP)
7	Pressure from employees require businesses to apply GA (CHEMPLO)
	The strategy of the business (STRATE)
8	Strategies for effective use of resources require businesses to apply GA (SRESOR)
9	Clean production strategy requires businesses to apply GA (SCLEA)
10	Ensuring the interests of stakeholders requires businesses to apply GA (SSHA)
	Characteristics of the business (CHARAC)
11	Production technology is updated with GA (CHPRO)
12	Managers' competencies ensure the application of GA (CHMANA))
13	Information systems ensure the application of GA (CHINFO)
14	Tools and methods of measuring inputs and outputs to enable GA measurement (CHAMEDS)
	Enterprise accounting system (ACCOU)
15	The level of accounting staff of the enterprise is capable of applying GA (ACAPA)
16	Accounting information system ensures GA application (AINFO)
17	Application of modern technology ensures GA application (ATECH)
	Applying green accounting (GA) (Dependent variable)
18	Using the product lifecycle method (GA1)
19	Using material flow method (GA2)
20	Use green design (GA3)
	Level sustainability of business (SUS) (Dependent variable)
21	Economically sustainable (SUS1)
22	Social sustainability (SUS2)
23	Environmentally sustainable (SUS3)

The hypotheses of the model:

H1: The legal regulatory system affects the application GA

H2: The characteristics of the supply chain affect the application of GA

H3: The strategy of business affects the application GA

H4: The enterprise accounting system affects the application GA

H5: The characteristics of enterprises affect the application of GA

H6: The legal regulatory system affects the level of sustainability of the business

H7: The characteristics of the supply chain affect the level of sustainability of a business

H8: The strategy of business affects the level of sustainability of a business

H9: The enterprise accounting system affects the level of sustainability of a business

H10: The characteristics of enterprises affect the level of sustainability of a business

H11: The application of GA affects the level of sustainability of a business

4.2.2. Factors affecting the application of GA and the level of sustainability of a business

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.875
Df	276
Sig.	.000

After running the rotation matrix, the coefficient KMO = 0.875 > 0.5, sig = 0.000 < 0.05, so the model is satisfactory, there are 7 groups of factors that converge and have cumulative loadings at 66.54% > 50%, which showed that the independent variables explained 66.54% of the dependent variable.

Table 4- Pattern Matrix^a

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
DOCU1					.805		

DOCU2				.844	
DOCU3				.704	
CHARAC1			.792		
CHARAC2			.854		
CHARAC3			.632		
CHARAC4			.558		
CHAIN1	.828				
CHAIN2	.861				
CHAIN3	.778				
CHAIN4	.803				
ACCOU1		.756			
ACCOU2		.713			
ACCOU3		.795			
ACCOU4		.924			
STRATE1					.935
STRATE2					.617
STRATE3					.716
GA1			.796		
GA2			.850		
GA3			.851		
SUS1				.714	
SUS2				.852	
SUS3				.812	

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

Pattern Matrix rotation matrix is used for the analysis of factor confirmatory in AMOS software, to see whether the factors are convergent and discriminant.

Table 5 - Regression Weights

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
GA	<---	STRATE	.369	.099	3.729	***	
GA	<---	ACCOU	.029	.096	.303	.762	
GA	<---	DOCU	.112	.128	.873	.383	
GA	<---	CHAIN	.213	.089	2.380	.017	
GA	<---	CHARAC	.359	.090	4.004	***	
SUS	<---	GA	.396	.106	3.728	***	
SUS	<---	DOCU	.023	.103	.226	.821	
SUS	<---	STRATE	.017	.099	.170	.865	
SUS	<---	CHARAC	.285	.143	1.996	.046	
SUS	<---	ACCOU	.401	.108	3.699	***	
SUS	<---	CHAIN	.261	.114	2.284	.022	

Regression Weights results (Table 5) show that: independent variables STRATE (Strategy of business), CHAIN (Characteristics of the supply chain), and CHARAC (Characteristics of business) have an impact on GA (sig < 0.05). Hypotheses H2, H3, H5 are accepted. The independent variables DOCU (Legal regulatory system), ACCOU (Enterprise accounting system) do not affect GA (sig > 0.05). Hypotheses H1, H4 are rejected. Similarly, variables CHAIN, ACCOU, CHARAC, GA have an impact on the dependent variable SUS (sig < 0.05). Hypotheses H7, H9, H10, H11 are accepted. The independent variable DOCU, STRATE do not affect SUS (sig > 0.05). Hypothesis H6, H8 is rejected.

Standardized Regression Weights results (Table 6) show that:

Impact on GA: The independent variable STRATE has the strongest impact with 0.374, followed by CHARAC (0.229), CHAIN (0.219); ACCOU and DOCU have no impact.

Impact on SUS: The intermediate variable GA has the strongest effect with 0.380, followed by CHAIN (0.229), CHARAC (0.225), ACCOU (0.017). DOCU and STRATE have no impact.

Table 6 - Standardized Regression Weights

			Estimate			Estimate	
GA	<---	STRATE	.374	CHARAC2	<---	CHARAC	.794
GA	<---	DOCU	-.028	CHARAC3	<---	CHARAC	.697
GA	<---	CHARAC	.229	CHARAC4	<---	CHARAC	.690
GA	<---	CHAIN	.219	STRATE1	<---	STRATE	.865
GA	<---	ACCOU	-.338	STRATE2	<---	STRATE	.669
SUS	<---	GA	.380	STRATE3	<---	STRATE	.763
SUS	<---	DOCU	-.023	DOCU1	<---	DOCU	.826
SUS	<---	ACCOU	.017	DOCU2	<---	DOCU	.805
SUS	<---	CHARAC	.225	DOCU3	<---	DOCU	.783
SUS	<---	STRATE	-.372	GA3	<---	GA	.807
SUS	<---	CHAIN	.229	GA2	<---	GA	.845
CHAIN1	<---	CHAIN	.831	GA1	<---	GA	.884
CHAIN2	<---	CHAIN	.867	SUS3	<---	SUS	.816
CHAIN3	<---	CHAIN	.850	SUS2	<---	SUS	.816
CHAIN4	<---	CHAIN	.817	SUS1	<---	SUS	.784
ACCOU1	<---	ACCOU	.828	CHARAC2	<---	CHARAC	.794
ACCOU2	<---	ACCOU	.819	CHARAC3	<---	CHARAC	.697

The summary results of the influences of factors on the application of GA and the sustainability of business are as follows:

Figure 1 – The influences of factors on the application of GA and the sustainability of the business

4.2.3. Differences in sustainability when applying GA

Out of 195 enterprises surveyed, 58 have applied GA. Testing the difference in the level sustainability of business between the two groups of having applied GA and having not applied GA through Independent-Samples T-Test, it shows that:

Table 7 - Group Statistics

	Application	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
SUS	1	58	4.21	.298	.039
	0	137	2.637	.665	.0568

Table 8 - Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
SUS	Equal variances assumed	51.048	.000	17.240	193	.000	1.57	.0910	1.39	1.749
	Equal variances not assumed			22.747	192.326	.000	1.569	.069	1.433	1.706

Since sig Levene's Test is less than 0.05, the variance between the two groups is different, we will use the sig T-Test value in the Equal variances not assumed row. The value of sig T-Test < 0.05, we conclude: There is a statistically significant difference in the level of sustainability between the two groups of enterprises that have applied GA and have not applied GA. Specifically, the group which has applied GA had an average level of sustainability at 4.21, the group that has not applied GA had a lower level of sustainability at 2.637.

5. Conclusion

The research synthesized macro and micro perspectives on green accounting, measurement methods used in green accounting such as environmental cost measurement, product life cycle cost measurement, activity-based billing (ABC). The article also analyzed that the application of green accounting can lead to the implementation of a "green" design for the production process, bringing benefits to the sustainable development of both businesses and society, which promotes businesses to voluntarily apply green accounting. The article also identified and measured the factors affecting the application of green accounting in enterprises, proving that the application of green accounting has an impact on the sustainable development of enterprises.

The research results showed that independent variables STRATE (Strategy of business), CHAIN (Characteristics of the supply chain), and CHARAC (Characteristics of business) have an impact on GA. The independent variables DOCU (Legal regulatory system), ACCOU (Enterprise accounting system) do not affect GA. Similarly, variables CHAIN, ACCOU, CHARAC, GA have an impact on the dependent variable SUS (sustainability of business). The independent variable DOCU, STRATE does not affect SUS. The independent variable STRATE has the strongest impact on GA, and ACCOU and DOCU have no impact. The intermediate variable GA has the strongest effect on SUS. DOCU and STRATE have no impact. This proved that the application of green accounting is determined by the enterprise's strategy. The characteristics of the business, as well as the characteristics of the supply chain also affected the adoption of green accounting. This is a reasonable reason because the application of green accounting is not only decided by business managers, but also by the cooperation of stakeholders in the supply chain and the specificity of production technology and qualifications of human resources. The next important thing is green accounting, which in turn has a positive influence on the level of sustainable development of the business. Besides, the characteristics of the supply chain, of the business, the accounting system also affected the sustainable development of the business.

The synthesis of previous studies also showed that green accounting is an issue related to environmental and ecological science, sustainable management of natural ecosystems, is new ideas and concepts in the field of environmental science. Solving the problem of rational use of resources, providing measurement and method of approach are the main contents of green accounting. Green accounting and its impact on cost reduction as a tool to improve the internal view of any economic entity. It is also a tool that provides important information for decision making, leading to optimal exploitation of resources, protection, and prevention of threats from the environment.

References

- Barbier, E.B., A. Markandya, and D.W. Pearce, 2018, "Environmental Sustainability and Cost-Benefit Analysis." *Environment and Planning A*, 259-263.
- Bernard, David, 1990, "Workgroup Issue Paper: Community or Ecosystem Level Indicators." *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 15, 282-282.
- Brown, Lester R. et al, 1993, *State of the World*. Washington, DC: Worldwatch Institute, 1993.
- Cairns, R.D. (2001), "Seeing the trees as a forest: what counts in green accounting", *Ecological Economics*, Vol. 36 No. 1, pp. 71-73.

- Chen, B., Dai, J. and Sciubba, E. (2014), "Ecological accounting for China based on extended exergy", *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Vol. 37, pp. 234-237.
- Cline, William R, 1992 *The Economics of Global Warming*. Washington DC: Institute for International Economics.
- Cucchiella, F., D'Adamo, I., Gastaldi, M., Lenny, K.S. and Rosa, P. (2017), "A comparison of environmental and energetic performance of european countries: a sustainability index", *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Vol. 78, pp. 201-205.
- Daly, H.E, 1990, "Toward Some Operational Principles of Sustainable Development." *Ecological Economics*, 34-37
- De Beer, P. and Friend, F. (2006), "Environmental accounting: a management tool for enhancing corporate environmental and economic performance", *Ecological Economics*, Vol. 58 No. 3, pp. 148-150.
- El Serafy, S. (1997), "Green accounting and economic policy", *Ecological Economics*, Vol. 21 No. 3, pp. 117-119.
- Farouk, S., Cherian, J. and Jacob, J. (2012), "Green accounting and management for sustainable manufacturing in developing countries", *International Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 7 No. 20, pp. 46-51.
- Hamoud Ismail, A., Abdul Rahman, A. and Ahmed Hezabr, A. (2018), "Determinants of corporate environmental disclosure quality of oil and gas industry in developing countries", *International Journal of Ethics and Systems*, Vol. 34 No. 4, pp. 127-132.
- Harrison, Anne, ed, 1989, *Introducing Natural Capital into the SNA*. New York: UNEP-World Bank Symposium, 45-47
- House, M.A, 1990, "Water Quality Indices as Indicators of Ecosystem Change." *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 15 (3 1990): 255-264.
- Huffman, E., 1990, "Workgroup Issue Paper: Indicators and Assessment of Agricultural Sustainability." *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 15 (3 1990): 303-306.
- Kawakita Jiro (1995), "An Introduction to Environmental Accounting As A Business Management Tool", pp. 120-122.
- Kuik, O. and H. Verbrugen, 1991, ed. *In Search of Indicators of Sustainable Development*. Vol. 1. Environment and Management. Dordrecht, Netherlands: Kluwer, 12-15
- Leung Pah Hang, M.Y., Martinez-Hernandez, E., Leach, M. and Yang, A. (2016), "Towards a coherent multi-level framework for resource accounting", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 125, pp.105-107.
- Mishan, E. J, 2017, *Cost Benefit Analysis: An Informal Introduction*. Allen and Unwin, London, 34-36
- Nasreen, S., Anwar, S. and Ozturk, I. (2017), "Financial stability, energy consumption and environmental quality: evidence from South Asian economies", *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Vol. 67, pp. 105-117.
- Norgaard, Richard and Richard Howarth, 1992, "Economics, Ethics and the Environment." In *The Energy-Environment Connection*, ed. Jack M. Hollander. 347-364. Washington DC: Island Press, 54-56
- Özokcu, S. and Özdemir, O. (2017), "Economic growth, energy, and environmental Kuznets curve", *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Vol. 72, pp. 139-143.
- Palisade, 1992, *Risk Analysis Simulation Add-In for Microsoft Excel*. Palisade Corporation, Newfield NY, 56-58
- Palmer, M. and Truong, Y. (2017), "The impact of technological green new product introductions on firm profitability", *Ecological Economics*, Vol. 136, pp. 76-80.
- Paul P. Craig, Harold Glasser, 1994, *5 Transfer Models for Green Accounting: An Approach to Environmental Policy Analysis for Sustainable Development*" National Research Council. *Assigning Economic Value to Natural Resources*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. doi: 10.17226/4844
- Pearce, David W. and Turner, R. Kerry. *Economics of Natural Resources and the Environment*. Baltimore, Johns Hopkins University Press, 1990.
- Stanojevic, M., Vranes , S. and Gö Kalp, I. (2010), "Green accounting for greener energy", *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Vol. 14, pp. 173-179.
- Turner, P. and Tschirhart, J. (2017), "Green accounting and the welfare gap", *Ecological Economics*, Vol. 30 No. 1, pp. 161-165.
- Turner, R. K., and Pearce, D. W, 1993, "Sustainable Economic Development: Economic and Ethical Principles", in *Economics and Ecology: New Frontiers and Sustainable Development*, edited by E. B. Barbier, Chapman and Hall, 47-54
- United Nations (1993), *Handbook of National Accounting System of Integrated Environmental and Economic Accounting – System of Integrated Environmental and Economic Accounting*.
- Wan, Y.K., Ng, R.T.L., Ng, D.K.S. and Tan Raymond, R. (2015), "Material flow cost accounting (GA)-based approach for prioritization of waste recovery", *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Vol. 107, 102-104.

Author Information

Prof. Dr. Nguyen Phu Giang
Thuongmai University

Dr. Tran Nguyen Bich Hien
Thuongmai University

Dr. Vu Thi Thu Huyen
Thuongmai University

MA. Luong Thi Hong Ngan
Thuongmai University

MA. Dao Ngoc Ha
Thuongmai University
